

Damage Assessment from Satellite Images for February 6 Kahramanmaraş Earthquakes: Deep Learning Approach Using VGG16 Network

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ABSTRACT

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The rapid and accurate detection of structural damages following earthquakes is of critical importance in disaster management processes. Traditional methods typically rely on detailed visual inspections conducted by experts, requiring significant time and effort during field operations. This presents a considerable challenge, particularly in large-scale disasters where swift response is essential. In recent years, machine learning and deep learning techniques have demonstrated significant potential to expedite these processes and improve accuracy. This study aims to detect post-earthquake building damages using the VGG16 deep learning model trained on satellite imagery obtained from regions affected by the earthquakes centered in Kahramanmaraş on February 6, 2023. The results from training and testing conducted on images collected via Google Earth Pro indicate that the proposed approach accurately distinguishes between damaged and undamaged buildings. Various activation functions were tested to identify the most optimal configuration to enhance the model's performance. Furthermore, the applicability of the proposed model to large-scale disaster scenarios demonstrates its potential to optimize processes and accelerate decision-making. This study highlights the impact of deep learning models in damage assessment, contributing significantly to the literature by expediting disaster management processes.

1. Introduction

Disasters cause significant destruction and damage worldwide. Their direct and indirect impacts involve elements that are difficult to measure and predict, leading to challenges in accurately assessing the associated losses [1]. Earthquakes, being one of the most devastating natural disasters due to their unpredictability, pose severe threats to human lives and habitats depending on their magnitude [2]. An earthquake occurs when energy accumulated in the Earth's crust is released, causing sometimes violent surface vibrations. This energy can result from the sudden movement of crustal segments, volcanic eruptions, or human-induced explosions, with most destructive earthquakes arising from crustal displacement [3]. Turkey's tectonic position places it within an active seismic zone, characterized by fault lines capable of producing high-magnitude earthquakes with severe and devastating impacts. [4]. Analysis of Turkey's seismic hazard map reveals that 96% of the country's land is located in earthquake-prone areas, where 98% of the population resides [5].

On February 6, 2023, a major earthquake in Kahramanmaraş, Turkey, consisting of two main shocks, severely affected a wide region and caused extensive destruction [6]. According to official sources, the earthquake resulted in 50,783 fatalities, 115,353 injuries, and the destruction of 37,984 buildings [7]. The Kahramanmaraş earthquake highlighted inadequacies in disaster risk reduction and preparedness activities, as well as deficiencies in the response phase due to the impact on 11 provinces [8]. Effective disaster management planning, encompassing both pre-event and post-event phases, is essential to minimize the loss of life and mitigate socio-economic disruptions caused by earthquakes.[9]. Factors influencing operational success in disaster management include timely response, effective information management, communication coordination, efficient resource utilization, and pre-disaster preparedness. Determining appropriate distribution strategies based on disaster types, managing resources and personnel, and coordinating all processes efficiently are key to enhancing operational capacity [10].

Disaster studies integrate theoretical and practical concepts from social and physical sciences, natural phenomena, and technological advancements. Technology can provide innovative solutions for disaster management [11]. Damage assessment models utilizing geographic and socio-economic data on GIS (Geographic Information System) platforms have been designed to estimate factors such as the quantity of collapsed buildings, casualties, and economic losses, based on earthquake magnitude and seismic location. These models have demonstrated high accuracy in estimating meizosismal areas and affected area intensities, achieving 97.5% and 76.5% accuracy, respectively [12]. Technological methods, such as real-time imaging with drones and high-resolution cameras, allow for rapid assessment of disaster-stricken areas [13]. Studies have shown that satellite imagery is an effective tool in post-earthquake damage assessments. For instance, SAR images taken prior to and following the 2006 Central Java earthquake were used to identify affected areas through correlation differences. [14]. Similarly, satellite imagery classification in the 2003 Algeria earthquake yielded consistent results for identifying collapsed buildings [15]. Advanced techniques using SPOT panchromatic satellite imagery have been employed to measure ground displacements with high precision [16]. Other studies propose synthetic generation of post-earthquake images using pre- and post-disaster satellite imagery for damage assessments [17]. Machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL) techniques have demonstrated greater efficiency and adaptability compared to conventional methods, requiring less manual intervention in the detection of structural damage based on vibration data. [18]. Numerous studies in the literature emphasize deep learning methods for assessing damage following earthquakes. Xu et al. [19] and Min et al. [20] utilized convolutional neural networks (CNNs) to identify and classify building damage from satellite images, demonstrating high accuracy. Similarly, applying three different CNN models to images taken before and after an earthquake for building damage identification revealed that a dual model outperformed the others. [21]. Xu et al. [22] introduced a dual-branch CNN that integrates spectral and spatial feature extraction from HSI data with feature extraction from LiDAR or high-resolution imagery, demonstrating superior performance. Research involving drone-acquired imagery has also been examined. Furkan et al. [23] conducted a comparison of the VGG16, YOLOv8, and Detectron2 deep learning algorithms for post-earthquake damage assessment based on drone images, concluding that YOLOv8 outperformed the others. A segmentation algorithm based on VGG16 was used to identify and delineate small, irregular cracks from high-resolution drone imagery after the MS 7.4 Maduo earthquake [24]. Comparisons of deep learning algorithms, such as VGG16, VGG19, and NASNet, for post-earthquake damage assessments revealed that VGG19 achieved the highest accuracy (90%) for classifying images as 'damaged' or 'normal,' showcasing the effectiveness of the VGG architecture [25]. In another study employing VGG16, 1,200 images were categorized into four levels of building damage, and the transfer learning model achieved 97.85% training accuracy and 89.38% validation accuracy, demonstrating potential for real-time application [26]. For the Kahramanmaraş earthquakes, AlexNet, VGG19, and ResNet50 algorithms were applied to classify building damage, with VGG19 achieving a validation accuracy of 79% [27]. These studies emphasize the efficacy of deep learning techniques in post-earthquake damage assessments and highlight their potential to address coordination challenges in disaster management.

This study aims to train a VGG deep learning model using pre- and post-earthquake satellite images of damaged and undamaged buildings collected from the regions affected by the February 6, 2023, Kahramanmaraş earthquakes. The trained model seeks to identify structural damage after potential earthquakes, thereby enabling coordinated disaster management scenarios. Google Earth Pro was used to obtain pre- and post-earthquake satellite images from the affected regions. These images were processed to be suitable for training the VGG16 model. The model's performance metrics for training and test datasets are presented in the study. This study aims to contribute to the literature by:

- Promoting the effective use of deep learning techniques for the rapid and accurate identification of structural damage.
- Providing an innovative solution for disaster management processes by offering a faster and more efficient approach than traditional field assessments.
- Enhancing large-scale disaster analyses by integrating satellite imagery with artificial intelligence methods to ensure more reliable and comprehensive evaluations.
- Offering a theoretical framework for the role of deep learning and artificial intelligence techniques in disaster management and providing insights into their potential performance in practical applications.

2. Material and Method

In this study, a dataset was first prepared using images obtained from earthquake-affected regions, and this dataset was divided into training, validation, and test sets. A deep learning model was selected for training, and activation functions and optimization algorithms to be used in the layers of the model were determined. Using evaluation metrics, the model's performance was measured on the training and validation datasets, while its overall performance was assessed on the test dataset. Performance metrics and corresponding graphs are presented in the Results and Discussion section.

2.1. Dataset

Satellite images of the regions affected by the earthquakes centered in Kahramanmaraş on February 6, 2023, were obtained using Google Earth Pro. This software provides high-resolution imagery from various regions worldwide, enabling the temporal analysis of changes in specific areas. Due to the occurrence of the earthquake during the winter season, clear images could not be obtained for certain parts of the affected areas. The imagery was acquired from the regions of Kahramanmaraş and Hatay. Post-earthquake images were compared with pre-earthquake images and subjected to labeling. The LabelMe Studio editor, an open-source tool for image annotation, was utilized for this process. The labeling was divided into "damaged" and "undamaged." In the labeled images, cropped building images marked as damaged and undamaged were prepared using JSON files and unlabeled visuals from the LabelMe Studio editor. The images were organized into two separate folders for damaged and undamaged buildings.

The process from acquiring satellite images to cropping damaged and undamaged buildings is illustrated in "Fig 1".

Fig. 1. The process involves acquiring satellite images of the earthquake-affected region before and after the event (I), comparing these images to identify damaged and undamaged buildings, which are then labeled as damaged (red) and undamaged (green) (II), and cropping the damaged and undamaged buildings from the collective image using these labels (III).

The varying dimensions of the cropped images introduce inconsistencies that hinder the model's ability to process them effectively. To address this issue, the bilinear interpolation method, a commonly used interpolation technique, was employed to standardize the image dimensions.

Bilinear interpolation is a resampling technique that estimates a new pixel value by calculating the distance-weighted average of the four nearest pixel values. This method is preferred in cases where the data in the original image needs to be preserved. It also gives faster results than the bicubic interpolation method [28]. After resizing, the images were fixed at 128x128 size.

2.2. VGGNET

VGGNet is a deep learning architecture designed for image classification and recognition tasks, introduced in 2014 by the Visual Geometry Group at the University of Oxford. The core variants of this architecture, VGG16 and VGG19, are deep convolutional neural network (CNN) models comprising 16 and 19 layers, respectively. The basic structure of these models is based on the idea of deepening the network using small convolutional filters of 3x3 size. VGGNet uses multiple convolutional layers of the same size in succession, and at the end of each group, there is a subsampling (pooling) layer. This arrangement gradually reduces the size of the feature maps while allowing the abstraction of high-level features. The deep structure of the model facilitates the learning of complex features, while small filter sizes keep the number of parameters under control. VGGNet is frequently preferred for transfer learning using pre-trained weights and can be easily adapted to different data sets. It is known for its high accuracy rates in image classification, object detection, and other computer vision tasks [31]. This study employs VGG16 due to its balance between computational efficiency and performance. Compared to deeper architectures like VGG19, VGG16 requires less computational power and memory while still achieving high accuracy. Its compatibility with limited hardware resources and its ability to generalize effectively with smaller datasets make it an ideal choice for this research.

2.2.1. VGG16 Deep Learning Architecture

VGG16 architecture includes 13 convolution layers, five pooling layers, and three fully connected layers. The model has six sections consisting of 5 consisting of convolution and pooling layers and one consisting of fully connected layers. Sixty-four filters of 3x3 size were used in the convolution layers in the first section, 128 filters of 3x3 size were used in the convolution layers in

the second section, 256 filters of 3x3 size were used in the convolution layers in the third section, 512 filters of 3x3 size were used in the convolution layers in the fourth and fifth sections, and max-pooling was applied with 2x2 filters in the pooling layers, which are the last layer of each section before the fully connected section. After the convolution and pooling steps, the flattening process is applied to the data in the section consisting of flattening layers, and the model's output is produced. The first two fully connected layers each contain 4096 channels, while the third, serving as the output layer, has 1000 channels, corresponding to the categories in the ImageNet dataset. The VGG16 deep learning architecture used is given in "Fig. 2".

Fig. 2. VGG16 Architecture (Adapted from [29])

2.3. Training Model

After the interpolation method, the fixed images were divided into training, validation, and test sets to train the model. For the training set, 70% of the images, i.e., 1549 images; Validation set, 15% of the images, i.e., 331 images; Test set, 15% of the images, i.e., 331 damaged and undamaged images, were used. Keras' ImageDataGenerator class was used to train the model. The ImageDataGenerator class is an important tool that facilitates data augmentation and preprocessing operations, especially when working with large data sets. This class provides various transformation techniques to transform images and make them suitable for dynamic model training. ImageDataGenerator can integrate the data into the training process by reading from disk to process data in a memory-friendly way and applying data augmentation operations to prevent overfitting [29]. Data augmentation and preprocessing steps were applied to the training data so that the model could generalize better. Random cropping, zooming, rescaling of pixel values of images in the range of 0-255 to 0-1, and random horizontal flipping were applied so that the model could better recognize symmetrical objects. The validation dataset was used to objectively assess the model's performance during training. It measured the model's performance without any data augmentation in the test dataset. The batch size of the model used was tested as 4, 8, 16, and 32, and since the best case was taken in a batch size of 32, training was done with 32 batches.

2.4. Activation Functions Used in the Model

Activation functions provide an important tool in solving nonlinear problems by enabling the outputs of neurons to be transformed nonlinearly. These functions increase the expressive power of artificial intelligence systems by enabling neural networks to learn more complex relationships [32]. Among the activation function types, swish, hard Swish, and relu activation functions were used in the convolution layer of the model, and sigmoid and softmax were used in the last layer activation function.

- **Relu:** The ReLU (Rectified Linear Unit) activation function is among deep learning models' most widely used activation functions. This function converts negative inputs to zero while leaving positive inputs as they are. ReLU enables deep networks to learn faster and more effectively, especially by reducing the problem of gradients approaching zero (vanishing gradient) [33].

- **Swish:** In recent years, the Swish activation function has emerged as an effective alternative in deep learning models. It is mathematically expressed as $f(x)=x \cdot \text{sigmoid}(x)$. Unlike ReLU, Swish produces small but non-zero values for negative values [34]. It works by multiplying the input values with the sigmoid function. It provides a smoother transition compared to other activation functions, and this feature can increase the accuracy, especially in deep learning models [35].
- **Hard Swish:** The Hard-Swish activation function was developed as a derivative of Swish and aims to offer less computational cost. Mathematically, it is defined as $f(x)=x \cdot \text{ReLU}(x+3)/6$ [36].
- **Sigmoid:** The sigmoid function is an activation function that compresses the input values between 0 and 1 nonlinearly and is mainly used in classification tasks [37].
- **Softmax:** The softmax activation function is a transformation function used to model the probabilities of more than one class. It normalizes the scores of each class and ensures that their sum is 1 [38].

2.5. Optimization Algorithm Used in the Model

Optimization algorithms are mathematical methods used to fit the parameters of a model to the training data. The aim is to increase the model's predictive accuracy by minimizing a loss function. These algorithms are usually based on the gradient descent method in deep learning. The AdaMax optimization algorithm used in this study is a generalized version of the Adam algorithm and works by scaling the second moment using the unbounded norm. This helps AdaMax to provide more stable and reliable optimization, especially in high-dimensional datasets. Unlike Adam, thanks to the use of the unbounded norm of the second moment, the effect of small gradients in the learning process is reduced, and the convergence performance of the algorithm is improved [39].

2.6. Evaluation of the Model and Evaluation Metrics

Various evaluation metrics were used to assess the training process and the overall performance of the deep learning model after training, as well as to visualize these results. These metrics provide comprehensive insights into the model's performance.

2.6.1. Evaluation Metrics

Evaluation metrics were applied to assess the overall performance of the model and to obtain detailed information regarding its accuracy. The metrics employed are as follows:

- **Accuracy:** It expresses the ratio of the examples the model correctly predicts to the total predictions. It provides a very effective and meaningful evaluation in data sets with balanced class distribution[40].
- **Loss:** Loss is a metric that quantifies the discrepancy between a machine learning model's predictions and the actual values, representing the model's error rate [41].
- **Precision:** Precision is a metric that measures the proportion of correctly predicted positive examples out of all the instances predicted as positive by the model [42].
- **Recall:** Recall is a metric that evaluates the model's ability to correctly identify examples from the positive class. It assesses how effectively the model captures true positive instances without missing them[42].
- **F1-Score:** The F1-Score is a metric that harmonizes Precision and Recall. By calculating their harmonic mean, it integrates the model's ability to correctly identify positive instances (Recall) with its ability to make accurate predictions (Precision) into a single, comprehensive measure[42].

- **ROC Curve:** ROC curve is a graphical representation used to evaluate the performance of a classification model at different threshold values. It depicts the relationship between the model's rate of true positives and its rate of false positives[43].
- **Confusion Matrix:** Confusion Matrix is a tool used to thoroughly analyze the prediction outcomes of a classification model. It shows the combination of the actual values and the values predicted by the model and is an important tool for understanding the types of classification errors [44].

2.6.2. Evaluation of the Model

The model is optimized with AdaMax in the optimization algorithm varieties. In order to find the best case for the model, six different combinations were evaluated, with Sigmoid and Softmax activation functions in the last layer and ReLU, Swish, and Hard-Swish functions in the intermediate layers. Comparisons between 6 different combinations were made with accuracy and loss metrics. After evaluating six scenarios, 30 runs were made in the case that gave the best value, and the average metric values were obtained. The model with the best accuracy performance across 30 runs was tested on the test data, and the confusion matrix was generated as part of the deep learning metrics.

3. Results and Discussion

The VGG16 network was tested in 6 cases with three activation function types used in the intermediate layers, two activation function types used in the last layer, and the Adamax optimization algorithm. The results of the 6 cases are given in “Table 1”.

Optimization algorithm	Activation function	Output Layer Function	Loss	Accuracy	Val_Loss	Val-Accuracy
Adamax	Relu	Sigmoid	0.0614	0.9774	0.1514	0.9456
Adamax	Relu	Softmax	0.0336	0.9877	0.2060	0.9275
Adamax	Swish	Sigmoid	0.0335	0.9903	0.1524	0.9547
Adamax	Swish	Softmax	0.0429	0.9858	0.1629	0.9456
Adamax	Hard Swish	Sigmoid	0.0213	0.9903	0.2009	0.9335
Adamax	Hard Swish	Softmax	0.0313	0.9871	0.1391	0.9607

Table 1. Results of the model according to 6 different situations

“Table 1” presents the effects of different activation function and output layer combinations on the model's performance using the Adamax optimization algorithm. The combination of Hard Swish as the intermediate activation function and Softmax as the output layer activation function achieved the lowest loss (0.0313) and the highest accuracy (96.07%) for both training and validation datasets. These results indicate that activation functions used in intermediate and output layers significantly influence the model's performance. This combination was executed in 30 runs, and the average values of the evaluation metrics obtained from these runs were calculated. The average values derived from these runs are provided in “Table 2”.

Optimization algorithm	Activation function (Hidden Layer-Output Layer)	Average accuracy	Average Loss	Average F1 Score	Average Recall	Average Precision s
Adamax	HardSwish-Softmax	0.9492	0.1801	0.9476	0.9492	0.9529

Table 2. Average metric values of 30 models

“Table 2” summarizes the average metric results obtained from 30 runs using the best-performing Hard Swish-Softmax combination. The average accuracy is 94.92%, the average F1 score is 94.76%, the average precision is 95.29%, and the average recall is 94.92%. These high values indicate that the model is successful in distinguishing between damaged and undamaged buildings during both the training and testing phases.

The ROC curve, generated by averaging the relevant metrics over 30 runs, is presented in “Fig. 5”.

Fig. 3. Average Roc Curve Graph

The model with the highest accuracy among 30 runs was tested using the test dataset. The accuracy graph of the model on the training and validation datasets is presented in “Fig. 4”, while the loss graph is shown in “Fig. 5”

Fig. 4. Accuracy graph of the best model

Fig. 5. Loss graph of the best model

“Fig. 4” and “Fig. 5” present the accuracy and loss curves, respectively, for both the training and validation phases. In “Fig. 4”, the training accuracy steadily increases, while the validation accuracy stabilizes at a certain point, indicating that the model has learned the training data but may struggle to generalize on the validation set. Similarly, in “Fig. 5”, the training loss decreases rapidly, whereas the validation loss fluctuates more, highlighting a disparity between the two. These differences suggest that the model would be improved with a larger, more diverse dataset and that the training process requires further optimization.

The confusion matrix obtained by running the model on the test dataset is presented in “Fig. 6”.

Fig. 6.Confusion matrix of the best model

“Figure 6” shows the confusion matrix generated using the test dataset consisting of 230 undamaged and 101 damaged building images. The model correctly classified all 230 undamaged building images as undamaged (True Positive) and did not incorrectly label any of them as damaged, indicating that the number of false negatives (False Negatives) was 0. Out of 101 damaged building images, 93 were correctly classified as damaged (True Negative), while 8 were incorrectly classified as undamaged (False Positive). These results show that the model is quite successful in distinguishing undamaged buildings. However, the model classified some damaged buildings as undamaged, which reveals its limitations, especially in detecting low-level damage.

4. Conclusion

This study was developed in response to the need for an effective and rapid assessment of the extensive damage caused by the February 6, 2023, earthquakes centered in Kahramanmaraş. The time-consuming and costly nature of traditional field inspections has increased the demand for the development of innovative deep learning-based methods. The potential of artificial intelligence and deep learning approaches to optimize post-disaster intervention processes has been the core motivation for this study. In this context, a deep learning approach is presented using satellite images for structural damage detection after the Kahramanmaraş-centered earthquakes of February 6, 2023. In the developed model, the VGG16 deep learning architecture was employed to classify damaged and undamaged buildings accurately. The model's performance was tested with various combinations of activation functions and the Adamax optimization algorithm; the best results were obtained with the Hard-Swish and Softmax combination. With this combination, the model achieved an accuracy of 96.07% and a loss value of 0.1211 on the validation dataset. Additionally, in 30 repeated experiments, the classification success on the test dataset, evaluated with performance metrics such as average accuracy, F1 score, precision, and recall, further supports the model's high performance.

This study provides a significant example of how deep learning-based damage detection models can be integrated into disaster management processes. Notably, the successful results achieved by the model using satellite imagery highlight its potential to significantly reduce the time and effort required for traditional field inspections. However, there are some disadvantages associated with the deep learning approach used. Since the model was trained with limited satellite images, its generalization capacity may be restricted, and its performance may be limited in different

geographical regions. Moreover, deep learning models trained on large datasets require high computational power and time-consuming training processes, which could present limitations in real-time analysis capabilities.

In this context, strengthening the model with different image processing techniques and data augmentation methods could enhance its applicability in larger geographical areas and various earthquake scenarios. The model is expected to contribute to rapid response processes following disasters and risk reduction and preparedness phases. Deep learning approaches provide high accuracy and reliability and can potentially optimize decision-making processes in large-scale disasters. Future studies plan to increase the model's generalization capacity by training it with larger datasets, enhancing real-time analysis capabilities, and testing faster deep learning architectures. Furthermore, data augmentation techniques and different image processing methods can optimize the model's performance. Future goals include integrating the model into pre-disaster risk assessment and preparedness processes, testing in complex disaster scenarios, and achieving a balance between accuracy and speed through hybrid models.

In conclusion, this study reveals the potential of artificial intelligence and deep learning methods to offer innovative solutions in disaster management. The results obtained provide significant contributions to both academic literature and practical applications.

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